

FREE-FLOW CARSHARING SYSTEMS IN A SPATIO-TEMPORAL URBAN ECOSYSTEM: AN URBAN INFORMATICS APPROACH.

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During the last years, sharing mobility is one of the emerging transport modes, but seldom its planning is entrusted to private operators and not seen as a major vector of urban mobility. The aim of this paper is to provide an extensive analysis of the relation between the utilization of carsharing vehicles and urban spatio-temporal patterns, focusing on the analysis of 4 weeks of free-flow carsharing data in the City of Milan. Since both temporal and spatial phenomena are influencing the carsharing demand, time-invariant factors (e.g., resident population density, etc.) and time-variant factors (e.g., public transport offer) were taken into consideration and analysed in relation to starting and ending point of rentals, and OD couples' characteristics. All the statistical analyses are performed on the weekday's and weekend's average values for each hour of the day, resulting in a series of daily utilization patterns unveiling the relationship between site-specific characteristics in respect to carsharing demand.

1. INTRODUCTION

The last two decades have been defined by a radical change in the urban mobility planning practice. If the 20th Century can be considered the Automotive City Era (Norton, 2008), driven by a car-centric approach, the 21st Century is characterized by the New Urbanism (Vanderbilt, 2010), as public mass-transit systems and low-emission modes are becoming the standard of planning.

In this framework, it is possible to appreciate the role of sharing mobility as one of emerging Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) solutions, capable of tackling the trade-off between the need for flexibility of private transport and the social/economic benefits of collective transport (Shaheen et al., 1998). Especially in Europe, shared mobility is considered as one of the strategic game-changers toward sustainable urban mobility by the SUMP Guidelines (Buhrmann et al., 2020).

For these reasons, during the last years European cities saw an increasing provision of free-flow carsharing systems: as of 2020, in Germany and Italy, free-flow carsharing operators are active, respectively, in 17 (BCS, 2020) and 5 (Osservatorio Nazionale Sharing Mobility, 2020) cities. The growing offer trend is also affecting the demand, with Germany users increasing by 140% from 2015 to 2020 (BCS, 2015; BCS, 2020).

In this context, the aim of the paper is to propose an innovative approach to understand carsharing utilization patterns by analysing trip data of a free-flow system in Milan,

Italy ², acquired in real-time through API endpoints during 4 weeks, from April 12th 2021 to May 09th 2021. Each trip data consists of the starting and ending points of the rental, with the respective timestamps, thus it can be located temporally and spatially in the urban territory. The analysed data adds up to a total of 312,406 starting and ending points (i.e., *Rental Events*), divided in weekday and weekend datasets in order to comprehend commuting-related phenomena. Since the aim of the research is to understand spatial and temporal relations, the statistical analyses are performed by looking at 60 minutes long timespans, allowing the authors to build daily profiles that describe the constantly changing factors influencing and shaping the mobility demand. For this reason, three categories of factors were considered: (i) Populations, namely resident and working population densities, (ii) Points of Interest, such as the density of diverse kind of amenities, and (iii) Public Transport offer.

The paper proposes a review of relevant studies focusing on sharing-mobility demand, especially in relation to urban characteristics, in order to describe the current research framework. Then, it presents the enabling data and methodology which sets the current work, and the results of the statistical analysis expressed as daily profiles. The paper concludes with final remarks about the achieved results, methodology limitations and future work.

1.1 Related works

The diffusion of carsharing services is rapidly increasing since the beginning of the century, similarly the scientific research in this field is steadily gaining momentum during the last decade, as free-flow systems are becoming the preferred choice of on-demand sharing mobility. The main difference introduced by free-flowing systems is that the vehicles are not linked to parking stations, de facto allowing a spontaneity and flexibility for the users (Kortum et al., 2012).

With this respect, traditional modelling approaches focus on the operational aspects of carsharing, both for station-based systems (Kek et al., 2006), free-flow systems (Kortum et al., 2012), and e-vehicle free-flow systems (Bruglieri et al. 2013), proposing allocation modelling methodology to properly locate vehicles and operational techniques to meet the demand. In this framework, it emerges how demographic characteristics and household density play an important role in mobility demand estimation (Kortum et al. 2012). Other approaches (Heilig et al., 2018) utilize agent-based travel demand models to further develop current planning tools to include this additional transport mode.

An alternative research track is proposed through a spatio-temporal approach, with the goal of analysing the relation between demand and external factors, such as weather and socio-demographic data (Schmöller et al. 2013), and subsequently by analysing time-defined spatial clusters of demand in relation with demographic distribution (Schmöller et al., 2015). Similarly, trip data has been analysed using GPS traces registering trips chains in relation to users' demographic characteristics (Leclerc et al., 2013).

2. ENABLING DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The main source of data used in the research is acquired in real-time through API endpoints of one of the carsharing operators active in Milan in the period comprised between April 06th 2021 and May 12th 2021. The information included in the dataset are the starting and ending points of each rental, with the associated geographical coordinates, timestamps and rental ID, thus all the information needed to spatially and temporally locate the *Events* (i.e., starting and ending of the rental) and the OD couple between the two points. The rest of the data used in the research is gathered from open-data sources and Google Places API queries and it is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 – List of datasets used in the research.

Time-variant Data				
Indicator	Dataset	Parameter	Source	Time Precision
Sharing Mobility	Rental events - Starting Points	<i>RE_S</i>	API ³	Minute ⁵
	Rental events – Ending Points	<i>RE_E</i>	API ³	Minute ⁵
	Rental OD Couple	<i>R_OD</i>	API ³	Minute ⁵
Public Transport Offer	Milan GTFS (from 06/04/2021 to 20/04/21)	<i>PT</i>	AMAT ⁴	Second ⁵
	Milan GTFS (from 20/04/2021 to 03/05/21)	<i>PT</i>	AMAT ⁴	Second ⁵
Time-invariant Data				
Indicator	Dataset	Parameter	Source	Year
Populations	Resident Population	<i>P_RP</i>	ISTAT ⁶	2011
	Working Population	<i>P_WP</i>	ISTAT ⁶	2011
Points of Interest ⁷	Civic Amenities	<i>POI_CA</i>	Places API ⁸	2021
	Commerce	<i>POI_Co</i>	Places API ⁸	2021
	Dining	<i>POI_Dn</i>	Places API ⁸	2021
	Recreation	<i>POI_Rc</i>	Places API ⁸	2021

2.1 Analysis timeframe and spatial constraints definition

Since the objective was to highlight patterns during weekdays and weekends, the overall data was selected in order to analyse 4 weeks, divided in two phases:

- Phase 1, spanning for 2 weeks (12 – 25 April, 2021), that was during a period of higher pandemic mobility restrictions in Milan (i.e., Zona Arancione ⁹);
- Phase 2, spanning for 2 weeks (26 April – 09 May, 2021), during which the restrictions were reduced (i.e., Zona Gialla ⁹).

In addition to this temporal constrains, the dataset was divided in weekdays (i.e., *Wd*) and weekends (i.e., *We*), based on the day of the week (Saturday and Sunday are considered weekend).

Subsequently, in order to perform statistical and spatial analyses, the rental dataset was referred to a grid, specifically the H3 hexagonal grid, proposed by Uber Engineering in 2018¹⁰. The number of hexagons included in the Milan Municipality border is 1,904, covering an extremely heterogeneous land use, for the purpose of this research the hexes were filtered so that only the cells with a number of *Events* greater than the 20th percentile (26.000) of the distribution were selected, resulting in 969 hexagons that were analysed, see Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1 – The total Number of Events per hexagon during weekdays and weekends in Phase 1 (left) and Phase 2 (right). The X axis is arranged spatially from the city centre to the external areas.

Therefore, the overall number of Rental Events (*RE*) considered in the analysis is 312,406 over a total of 315,435 for the same timeframe, where the excluded portion accounts for about the 1% of the dataset. The exclusion of the lower 20th percentile was performed in order to consider only cells with actual utilization patterns and it was considered on the overall number of Rental Events.

Figure 2 – Map showing the overall number of Rental Events and the hexes selection based on the 20th percentile (26.000). In addition to the lower values, also the hexes outside the Municipality borders are excluded.

The Rental Events datasets were used to analyse the relation between the position of the events and the urban characteristics. Conceptually, the authors considered the Starting set (*RE_S*) and Ending set (*RE_E*) as two separate datasets, taking into account exclusively the spatial and temporal position of such events.

On the other hand, the Rental OD Couple dataset (*R_OD*) is based on the relation between the Events of the same trip. For this reason, the dataset is cleaned from (i) the trips originating or ending outside the selected hexes, and from (ii) the trips shorter than 5 minutes or longer than 90 minutes ¹¹. Data validation resulted in 141,205 OD couples, defined by a starting hex, an ending hex and a duration. As shown in Figure 3, trips differ in duration and most of them are from 20 to 30 minutes long. Since the OD data is based on the starting and ending point of each rental, the actual route is not known, so the metric length of the trip will not be analysed in this research ¹².

Figure 3 – The distribution of the trip durations and the percentage of the trip typologies. It is possible to see how a large portion of the trips starts outside the Low Emission Zone of Milan (LEZ / Area C) to end outside it as well.

2.2 Spatio-Temporal Urban Data analyses

The H3 hexagons were also used to aggregate Urban Data, so that each hex would represent a sum, or an average value, that could be comparable across the city. In order to perform the spatial join, a two-step process was devised. Firstly, a buffer of 300 meters of radius, considered as a 5-minutes walking distance, was calculated from each Rental Event. The buffer was used to count the number of Points of Interest located in the proximity of each Event and the average Populations density. Secondly, the values calculated for each buffer were joined with the hexagon, by joining the position of the related Event point, and the average values per parameter were calculated. The process is illustrated in Figure 4 and it was preferred to a simply spatial join on the hexagonal grid because it takes into consideration the location of each Event, avoiding the edge-effect due to data aggregation ¹³.

Moreover, for the purpose of comparing the various parameters, the Urban Data (i.e., Populations and Points of Interest) were normalized on a 0 – 1 scale, creating Z-scores that follow the normal distribution of the values. On the other hand, the Rental Events parameters (i.e., *RE_S* and *RE_E*) were rescaled to the same interval using a min – max normalization.

Figure 4 – The diagram explains the two-step process to aggregate Urban Data on the hexagonal grid.

Conceptually, the intent of the analyses based on the Urban Data is to understand how each parameter is influencing the carsharing demand (Rental Events), by taking into account both the spatial and the temporal location. From an exploratory data analysis, no noticeable differences emerged from the comparison between the two phases, on the contrary, weekday and weekend demand are more heterogenous, therefore the datasets were aggregated maintaining only the latter segmentation. For these reasons the demand data was arranged in 4 datasets, visible in Table 2, that are involved in the calculation of a series of correlations and multiple linear regression models between the *RE* datasets and the Urban Data.

Table 2 – Datasets used in the analyses in relation with Urban Data. The average hex count expresses the average number of events per hex and the average 60-minutes count is the average number of events in the 60-minutes timespans (calculated excluding the night).

Parameter	Dataset	Events count (from 00 to 24)	Average hex count (from 00 to 24)	Average 60-minutes count (from 06 to 24)
WD_RE_S	Weekday Rental Events – Starting Points	109,671	113.180	5,919.944
WD_RE_E	Weekday Rental Events – Ending Points	109,611	113.118	5,896.722
WE_RE_S	Weekend Rental Events – Starting Points	46,568	48.107	2,430.111
WE_RE_E	Weekend Rental Events – Ending Points	46,556	48.195	2,402.778

To understand the heterogenous factors that shape the demand, the task was split in smaller portions and different analyses for each dataset, in particular: (i) a series of correlations (using Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient) between the normalized values of Resident Population (*Z_P_RP*) and Working Population (*Z_P_WP*) and the normalized Events datasets, aimed at understanding the systematic relation between households, working places and carsharing demand ¹⁵; (ii) a series of multiple linear regression models between the normalized Events datasets as dependent variables and the normalized values of the Points of Interest datasets (*Z_POI_CA*, *Z_POI_Co*, *Z_POI_Dn*, *Z_POI_Rc*) as independent variables, aimed at understanding the role of each typology of amenity in relation to the carsharing demand ¹⁵. These calculations

are performed for each of the 60 minutes long timespans, in order to build a daily profile able to represent the time-variant nature of the demand.

Figure 5 – Maps showing the distribution of Z-scores of time-invariant Urban Data. It is possible to notice how spatial patterns repeat themselves between different parameters.

In addition to this, the spatial-autocorrelation between the two Population datasets (P_{RP} , P_{WP}) was considered. In particular, using the Bivariate Moran analysis ¹⁴ (Anselin et al., 2002) with a weight matrix based on a Queen contingency of $k = 1$, the hexes positively correlated between the two parameters are excluded from the following calculations. This step allowed to exclude 98 hexes where both parameters express similar density values and would not add significance to the correlation analyses, see Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Map showing the location of spatial correlation between the two Populations datasets (Z_P_RP , Z_P_WP). The hexes positively correlated (High – High) are excluded from the correlation analyses.

2.4 Public transport cost-comparison analysis

The relation between public transport and carsharing demand is analysed using the OD couple datasets (R_OD). Meanwhile the Events datasets were segmented into subsets, the trips dataset is analysed without splitting it, because it is compared to another time-variant parameter (i.e., the public transport offer calculated from the GTFS).

In order to calculate the cost (expressed in minutes) of the public transport mode, every trip was simulated using a routable multimodal network, built using the GTFS data, hence time-variant. The simulation allowed to compute a multimodal travel time as the trip was occurring at the same time of the carsharing trip¹⁵. The computed travel time is dependent from the public transport offer, because among the information stored in the GTFS, the exact departure time is available, meaning that the same route in different moments of the day could lead to different outputs.

Since the public transport role is linked to the OD and not to the single event, the approach for this analysis is different: the purpose is to compare the carsharing travel time with the public transport travel time. For this reason, the data is analysed in 60 minutes timespans and the comparison is between the mean travel time measures of a matrix built starting from the hexes (969x969).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Events based analyses

The analyses were aimed at identifying relations between Urban Data and carsharing demand. The first portion of the outcomes consists in a series of correlations between the Events datasets, which represent the origins and the destinations of the demand,

and the Populations datasets. The results of the analyses are arranged by Starting Points and Ending Points, for the weekday dataset (see Table 3 and Figure 7) and for the weekend dataset (see Table 4 and Figure 8).

Table 3 – Correlation analyses results for the weekday. Not-significant p-values are highlighted in bold. The number of samples for all correlations is n = 1742.

	Starting Points				Ending Points			
	Z_P_RP		Z_P_WP		Z_P_RP		Z_WP	
	r	p < .001	r	p < .001	r	p < .001	r	p < .001
00:00	.211	•	.236	•	.274	•	.183	•
01:00	.198	•	.167	•	.221	•	.134	•
02:00	.154	•	.123	•	.162	•	.061	.011
03:00	.125	•	.072	.003	.081	.001	.072	.003
04:00	.163	•	.048	.046	.069	.004	.090	•
05:00	.318	•	.032	.188	.014	.571	.113	•
06:00	.320	•	.001	.972	.014	.562	.252	•
07:00	.401	•	.132	•	-.051	.032	.252	•
08:00	.340	•	.277	•	-.008	.747	.403	•
09:00	.212	•	.416	•	-.033	.172	.493	•
10:00	.164	•	.497	•	.070	.003	.570	•
11:00	.085	•	.556	•	.103	•	.574	•
12:00	.099	•	.598	•	.153	•	.569	•
13:00	.075	.002	.628	•	.167	•	.587	•
14:00	.132	•	.572	•	.162	•	.548	•
15:00	.123	•	.593	•	.181	•	.557	•
16:00	.154	•	.561	•	.210	•	.505	•
17:00	.133	•	.595	•	.258	•	.518	•
18:00	.219	•	.498	•	.323	•	.432	•
19:00	.309	•	.440	•	.350	•	.391	•
20:00	.273	•	.430	•	.393	•	.364	•
21:00	.305	•	.382	•	.406	•	.298	•
22:00	.329	•	.320	•	.427	•	.249	•
23:00	.299	•	.299	•	.400	•	.227	•

Figure 7 – Daily profiles of the correlation analyses for the weekday. Not-significant values are displayed with indicators on the lines.

Table 4 – Correlation analyses results for the weekend. Not-significant p-values are highlighted in bold. The number of samples for all correlations is n = 1742.

	Starting Points				Ending Points			
	Z_P_RP		Z_P_WP		Z_P_RP		Z_WP	
	r	p < .001	r	p < .001	r	p < .001	r	p < .001
00:00	.276	•	.239	•	.323	•	.188	•
01:00	.196	•	.234	•	.282	•	.167	•
02:00	.107	•	.163	•	.218	•	.149	.011
03:00	.115	•	.151	•	.141	•	.121	.003
04:00	.086	•	.100	•	.060	.013	.117	•
05:00	.176	•	.080	.001	.068	.004	.129	•
06:00	.231	•	.026	.280	.006	.814	.210	•
07:00	.254	•	.078	.001	.008	.734	.201	•
08:00	.271	•	.144	•	.068	.004	.267	•
09:00	.379	•	.202	•	.160	•	.338	•
10:00	.293	•	.278	•	.149	•	.366	•
11:00	.245	•	.371	•	.188	•	.420	•
12:00	.209	•	.429	•	.204	•	.413	•
13:00	.237	•	.411	•	.227	•	.408	•
14:00	.168	•	.426	•	.199	•	.425	•
15:00	.184	•	.433	•	.188	•	.450	•
16:00	.214	•	.443	•	.182	•	.453	•
17:00	.195	•	.420	•	.207	•	.423	•
18:00	.215	•	.414	•	.268	•	.415	•
19:00	.237	•	.424	•	.322	•	.388	•
20:00	.263	•	.379	•	.356	•	.338	•
21:00	.296	•	.327	•	.360	•	.284	•
22:00	.352	•	.250	•	.390	•	.224	•
23:00	.298	•	.244	•	.345	•	.174	•

Figure 8 – Daily profiles of the correlation analyses for the weekend. Not-significant values are displayed with indicators on the lines.

The results of the multiple regression models between the demand datasets and the POI datasets are expressed as charts for the four dependent values datasets (i.e., *WD_RE_S*, *WD_RE_E*, *WE_RE_S* and *WE_RE_E*). The outputs are organized as daily profiles, showing only the results where the model has an adjusted r square value ≥ 0.3 . The Beta coefficient values for the four Points of Interest parameters are expressed only if significant (P value < 0.05).

Figure 8 – Chart showing the multiple linear regression models based on the Weekday Starting Points datasets (*WD_RE_S*) and the Weekday Ending Points datasets (*WD_RE_E*). Not-significant Beta coefficients (P value ≥ 0.05) are not shown.

Figure 9 – Chart showing the multiple linear regression models based on the Weekend Starting Points datasets (*WE_RE_S*) and the Weekend Ending Points datasets (*WE_RE_E*). Not-significant Beta coefficients (P value ≥ 0.05) are not shown.

3.2 Trip based analysis

The goal of the cost comparison between the carsharing trips and the public transport simulated travel time was to understand how two competing mobility choices perform with a direct comparison. The cost, expressed in minute and aggregated per hex, is directly comparable since: (i) for the carsharing trips is measured between the starting and ending points, (ii) for the public transport is simulated at the same time of the former, on a multimodal routable network.

To enhance the readability of the outcomes, the results are divided with the same categories shown in Figure 3, taking into account the role of Area C / LEZ (Low Emission Zone) in Milan.

Figure 10 – Average cost comparison between carsharing and public transport. The total carsharing and public transport cost metric is the average value without considering the role of Area C / LEZ in Milan, and can be interpreted as a reference measure.

4. DISCUSSION

The analyses proposed in this research try to describe different aspects of the same framework: the sharing mobility utilization in an urban environment. Generally speaking, the mobility patterns of a city are defined by numerous and heterogenous factors, that hardly can be summarized in a single analysis. The roles of different kinds of mobility demand (e.g., work commuting, study commuting, occasional, touristic, etc.) and the availability of several modes (e.g., private cars, sharing mobility, public transport, soft mobility, etc.) account to the definition of a complex system that can be studied more effectively by looking at smaller portions.

With this consideration in mind, this research aims to split the problem in smaller tasks, by looking at: (i) systematic mobility, with the correlation analyses between Rentals Events and Populations datasets; (ii) occasional mobility, with the multiple linear regression models between the Rental Events and the Points of Interest datasets; (iii) Public Transport as a competitive mode, with the cost comparison analysis between the OD couples dataset and the simulated TP cost.

These typologies of analyses were defined after a thorough process of exploratory data analysis, during which different kinds of analyses were discarded since the results were not conclusive. As an example, a series of correlation analyses were tested to understand the relation between the simulated cost of public transport and the number of trips on the same OD relation. However, it appears that there is not a significant correlation between the two metrics, that is counter-intuitive if we consider the carsharing as a competing mode in respect to the public transport. Also, as visible in Figure 10 - D, it appears that the cost comparison does not reveal significant differences during the hours between 08:00 and 19:00, meanwhile for the early morning and late evening, it is possible to see how the sharing mobility appears as much faster alternative, that is mainly due to the fact that the public transport offer is reduced during off-peak hours. On the other hand, in Figure 10 - B / C, it is possible to appreciate how during the peak-hours (07:00 – 09:00 and 17:00 – 19:00) the carsharing is affected by the traffic congestion making the cost is noticeably higher than the public transport, therefore it should not be considered as a valid alternative for the systematic mobility.

This concept can be expanded by looking at the correlation analyses results. The relation between the Rental Events and the Resident Population (P_{RP}) dataset was expected to be higher during the weekdays and lower during the weekends, and the results confirmed this hypothesis. The fact that the correlations are weak or moderate can be explained by the fact stated at the beginning of this section: carsharing mobility patterns are not influenced by a single factor, so a strong correlation was not expected and the focus is more on the relative weights of these values.

Another confirmed hypothesis is the difference between the WD_{RE}_S and WD_{RE}_E datasets, that describe respectively the origins and the destinations. The r values are higher during the morning peak hour for the origins and during the afternoon peak hour for the destinations, showing a systematic usage pattern.

On the contrary, the Working Population (P_{WP}) results should be interpreted in a different way: the correlation coefficients seem to suggest a stronger relation with the Rental Events datasets, but in the authors' opinion, this result cannot be completely explained as systematic mobility. As visible in Figure 5, the density of the Working Population is radially distributed in the urban territory, with higher values in the city centre and lower toward the edges of the Municipality. The same mono-centric pattern is noticeable in the Points of Interest density distributions, therefore the correlation with the Working Population could be explained by the compresence of other factors, such as the amenities. To support this hypothesis, a spatial-autocorrelation analysis, visible in Figure 11, shows the relation between $Z_{P_{WP}}$ dataset and an average POI density dataset (Z_{POI}). The Bivariate Moran analysis ¹⁴ (Anselin et al. 2002), with a weight matrix based on a Queen contingency of $k = 1$, shows a large portion of the city centre with a High – High cluster between the two parameters, suggesting the presence of comparably high densities between workplaces and amenities.

Figure 11 – Map showing the location of spatial correlation between the Working Population dataset ($Z_{P_{WP}}$) and an average POI density dataset (Z_{POI}).

As visible in Tables 3 and 4, the correlation coefficients between $Z_{P_{WP}}$ and the Rental Events datasets are compatible with the outputs of the multiple linear regression models. During the hours with coefficients showing a stronger relation, also the regression models show a higher reliability, ranging from adjusted r squared values between 0.302 and 0.485. Considering these profiles as a method to understand the role of occasional mobility, the Beta coefficients values associated to the significant POI parameters can be referred as the relative weights of the influence of each amenity typology on the carsharing demand. Generally speaking, Figures 8 and 9 confirm expected patterns: (i) Dining and Recreation datasets have a stronger weight during the evening, (ii) Commerce dataset influences negatively the demand during the evening, (iii) Civic Amenities dataset weight ceases to exist after office business hours.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The aim of this research was to propose a spatio-temporal interpretation of carsharing demand data, by looking both at the starting and ending points of the rentals and the trips' information. The analyses take into account the time-variant nature of mobility data by merging demand patterns with time-invariant Urban Data and time-variant Public Transport offer, proposing a methodology structured as a heuristic approach to understand a complex and stratified phenomenon.

The results of the analyses manage to describe partially three of the identified influencing factors of carsharing utilization patterns, namely *(i)* systematic mobility, *(ii)* occasional mobility and *(iii)* relation with public transport. In particular, one of the expected outcomes is the role of systematic and occasional mobility. The outputs of the Events based analyses suggest how weakly carsharing correlates with commuting patterns, both from the perspective of the origins (i.e., Resident Population) and the destinations (i.e., Working Population), and vice-versa for the afternoon peak hour. On the contrary, the occasional mobility appears as one of the main demand-influencing factors, which is comprehensible given that the actual monetary cost of MaaS systems is generally significantly higher than public transport or alternative modes. Sharing mobility is inherently based on a service-based business model, which is not entirely compatible with systematic patterns, unless subscription models are implemented. Instead, the occasional mobility appears as a suitable user behaviour typology, with an occasional return trip to the place of residence at the end of the day, see Table 3 and Figure 7.

Finally, the trip based analysis shows how the temporal costs of carsharing and public transport vary greatly during the day. As visible in Figure 10, during the daily business hours the public transport is generally preferable to carsharing, that is mainly due because Milan public transport offer is high. The roles become inverted as soon as the offer is lower, especially after the afternoon peak (20:00 – 24:00) and before the morning peak (00:00 – 07:00). This outcome contributes to confirm the hypothesis that sharing mobility is inadequate to cope with systematic mobility, because it cannot be considered as time-competitive with alternative modes.

Future works aim to perform the same typologies of analyses on other cities, to understand if the conclusions drawn from this research are site-specific or related to the urban morphology and sociality. Moreover, the data used in this paper did not have users' profile information, that would be crucial in order to understand patterns linked to demography profile or income status. Finally, the access to other data sources, such as public transport demand data, could enable a direct comparison between competing modes aimed at deepening the understanding of sharing mobility and public transport relation.

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Notes

1. Supervising Co-Author
2. In order not to disclose sensitive information, the authors elected to not reveal the carsharing operator company.
3. The API endpoint was interrogated every minute April 06th 2021 and May 12th 2021 and the database was structured by the rental events daily.
4. GTFS data for Milan Municipality is maintained and published by Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente Territorio (AMAT) and was downloaded from transitfeed.com because it allowed the access to the feeds' archives.
5. Even if data allowed a minute and second wise precision, all the time-variant data was aggregated at an hour level.
6. Population data is published by the Italian Statistical Institute (Istituto Nazionale di Statistica – ISTAT), specifically the resident population data is from “Censimento della popolazione e delle abitazioni” and the working population data is from “Censimento dell’industria e dei servizi”, both published in 2011. No fine-grained population datasets are available at the moment of the research.
7. Even if Points of Interest could be considered as a time-variant data, since they are active or inactive in different hours of the day, for the scope of this research they were considered as time-invariant as landuse characteristics.
8. Google Places API was interrogated to access the location and the typologies of points of interests in Milan Municipality.
9. The complete restriction timeline can be found here (in Italian):
https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gestione_della_pandemia_di_COVID-19_in_Italia#Obbligo_di_certificazione_verde_e_nuovi_parametri_per_gli_scenari
The main difference between Zona Gialla and Zona Arancione is the opening of entertainment venues (e.g., theatres and cinemas) and dining venues, only in outside areas.
10. Among the several resolutions available for the H3 grid, the current work adopted the one characterized by cells with an average diameter of the circumscribed circle of 395 meters.
11. The carsharing rentals can be prolonged for several hours, while doing several stops with the vehicle, or for several days, therefore the maximum cut-off is introduced to filter multi-stop trips and long rentals, since they fall out of scope in respect to the proposed research.
12. The starting and ending points of the rental allow the simulation of a shortest path, that could be considered as the route. However, since it does not consider other route choices factors, the authors' choice is to consider just the trip duration that can be considered as more reliable.
13. Except for the Public Transport simulation, all the GIS analyses are done on QGIS 3.20.

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14. All the spatial correlation calculations have been performed using the software GeoDa 1.18, available here: <https://geodacenter.github.io/>
15. Statistical analyses (correlation analyses and multiple linear regression models) have been performed using the software IBM SPSS Statistics v.27.
16. The Public Transport simulation, using a multimodal routable network derived from GTFS data have been performed using ESRI ArcMap 10.8 and Network Analyst Extension.